

The Announcer Trainee Satisfaction by National Broadcasting and Telecommunications Commission of Thailand

Nareenad Panbun

Abstract—The objective is to study the knowledge utilization from the participants of the announcer training program by National Broadcasting and Telecommunications Commission (NBTC). This study is a quantitative research based on surveys and self-answering questionnaires. The population of this study is 100 participants randomly chosen by non-probability sampling method. The results have shown that most of the participants were satisfied with the topics of general knowledge about the broadcasting and television business for 37 people representing 37%, followed by the topics of broadcasting techniques. The legal issues, consumer rights, television business ethics, and credibility of the media are, in addition to the media's role and responsibilities in society, the use of language for successful communication. Therefore, the communication language skills are the most important for all of the trainees and will also build up the image of the broadcasting center.

Keywords—Announcer training program, participant, requirements announced, theory of utilization.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE present the radio and television broadcasting affairs have a various pattern in terms of broadcasting radio and TV channels. They announce station program information, such as program schedules and station breaks for commercials, or public service information, and they introduce and close programs. Announcers read prepared scripts or make ad lib commentary on the air, as they present news, sports, the weather, time, and commercials. If a written script is required, they may do the research and writing. The announcer also has to interview the guests or moderate in the panel discussion. Some of them have to give the comments for the sporting events, parades and other occasions. Therefore, the announcer has to be well known by the audiences and the radio and television broadcasters. In addition, the announcer has to carry and control signal monitoring, advertise commercial advertisers, keep a record of the station's daily programming, and produce advertisements and other recorded material as well [1]. Nowadays, the advances in changing technology will make any job task of the announcer efficiency demanding. All of the announcer staff need to have some previous experience and carry out editorial and technical broadcast work.

At many music stations, the NBTC of Thailand is simultaneously responsible for both announcing and operating

the control board, which is used to broadcast programming, commercials, and public-service announcements according to the station's schedule. Much of the recorded material that used to be on records or tape is now in the form of digital files on computers. Public radio and television announcers are involved in station fundraising efforts. Changes in technology have led to more remote operation of stations. Several stations in different locations of the same region may be operated from one office. Some stations operate overnight without any staff, playing programming from a satellite feed or using programming that was recorded earlier, including segments from announcers. Announcers frequently participate in community activities. Sports announcers, for example, may serve as masters of ceremonies at sports club banquets or may greet customers at openings of sporting goods stores. Radio announcers who broadcast music often are called disc jockeys (DJs). Some DJs specialize in one kind of music, announcing selections as they air them. Most DJs do not select much of the music they play (although they often did so in the past); instead, they follow schedules of commercials, talk, and music provided to them by management. While on the air, DJs Comment on the music, weather, and traffic. They may take requests from listeners, interview guests, and manage listener contests. Some DJs announce and play music at clubs, dances, restaurants, and weddings [2]. They often have their own equipment with which to play the music. Many are self-employed and rent their services out on a job-by-job basis. Show hosts may specialize in a certain area of interest, such as politics, personal finance, sports, or health. The NBTC of Thailand contribute to the preparation of the program's content, interview guests, and discuss issues with viewers, listeners, or the studio audience. Formal training in broadcasting from a college, a technical school, or a private broadcasting school is valuable. These programs prepare students to work with emerging technologies, a skill that is becoming increasingly important. Many announcers have a bachelor's degree in a subject such as communications, broadcasting, or journalism. High school and college courses in English, public speaking, drama, foreign languages, and computer science are valuable, and hobbies such as sports and music are additional assets. The NBTC of Thailand considering enrolling in a broadcasting school should contact personnel managers of radio and television stations, as well as broadcasting trade organizations, to determine Announcers are often required to complete long-term on-the job training [3].

Nareenad Panbun is with Faculty of Management Science, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand (e-mail: nareenad.pa@ssru.ac.th).

This can be accomplished at campus radio or TV facilities and at commercial stations while students serve as interns. Paid or unpaid internships provide students with hands-on training and the chance to establish contacts in the industry. Unpaid interns often receive college credit and are allowed to observe and assist station employees. Although the Fair Labor Standards Act limits the amount of work that unpaid interns may perform in a station, unpaid internships are more common than paid internships. Unpaid internships sometimes lead to paid internships, however, which are valuable because interns do work ordinarily performed by regular employees and may even go on the air. Once hired by a television station, an employee usually starts out as a production assistant, researcher, or reporter and is given a chance to move into announcing if they show an aptitude for "on-air" work. A beginner's chance of landing an on-air job is remote. The best chances for an on-air job for inexperienced announcers may be as a substitute for a familiar announcer at a small radio station or on the late-night shift at a larger station. The NBTC of Thailand in radio, newcomers usually start out taping interviews and operating equipment. The school's reputation for producing suitably trained candidates [4].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Announcer Training Program

Entry into this occupation is highly competitive, and postsecondary education or long-term on-the-job training is common. Trainees usually must have several years of experience in the industry before receiving an opportunity to work on the air. An applicant's delivery and—in television—appearance and style is important [5].

1. Laws

Some job openings will arise from the need to replace those who transfer to other kinds of work or leave the labor force. Nevertheless, competition for jobs as announcers will be keen because the broadcasting field attracts many more jobseekers than there are jobs. Small radio stations are more inclined to hire beginners, but the pay is low. Applicants who have completed internships and those with related work experience usually receive preference for available positions with good computer and technical skills also will have an advantage because announcers are now doing more of the computer work that was previously carried out by technicians. In radio, announcers are increasingly using computers to edit their programs. Because competition for ratings is so intense in major metropolitan areas, large stations will continue to seek announcers who have proven that they can attract and retain a sizable audience. Announcers who are knowledgeable about business, consumer, and health news also may have an advantage over others. While subject-matter specialization is more common at large stations and the networks, many small stations also encourage it. There will be some opportunities for self-employed DJ's who provide music at clubs and special events but most of these jobs will be part time.

B. Consumer Rights

Consumer Rights system announcers provide information to the audience at sporting, performing arts, and other events. Consumer Rights announcers usually work in well-lighted, air-conditioned, soundproof studios. Announcers often work within tight schedules, which can be physically and mentally stressful. For many announcers, the intangible rewards—creative work, many personal contacts, and the satisfaction of becoming widely known—far outweigh the disadvantages of irregular and often unpredictable hours, work pressures, and disrupted personal lives. The broadcast day is long for radio and TV stations—many are on the air 24 hours a day—so announcers can expect to work unusual hours. Many present early-morning shows, when most people are getting ready for work or commuting, while others do late-night programs. The shifts, however, may not be as varied as in the past because new technology is allowing stations to eliminate some of the overnight hours [6].

1. Ethics

Announcers must have a pleasant and well-controlled voice, good timing, excellent pronunciation, and correct grammar. College broadcasting programs offer courses, such as voice and diction, to help students improve their vocal qualities. Television announcers need a neat, pleasing appearance as well. Knowledge of theater, sports, music, business, politics, and other subjects likely to be covered in broadcasts improves one's chances for success. Announcers, especially those seeking radio careers, should have good information technology skills and be capable of using computers, editing equipment, and other broadcast-related devices because new advances in technology have made these abilities increasingly important. Announcers also need strong writing skills, because they normally write their own material. In addition, they should be able to ad lib all or part of a show and to work under tight deadlines. The most successful announcers attract a large audience by combining a pleasing personality and voice with an appealing style [7].

III. METHODOLOGY

The participants were students of the Radio Announcing Course of the NBTC of Thailand, in Thailand. People interested in doing the course go through a selection test carried out by the voice-over teacher and the SLP. In readings of two radio-like texts, one piece of news and an advertisement, the following parameters are evaluated: reading, pronunciation, articulation, interpretation, projection, consumer rights, and Ethic and voice quality [8].

A. Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, version 20.0. Means and percentages were calculated for the perceptual analysis values. Intrajudge reliability was measured considering then repeated stimuli. The 100 Announcer t test was used for paired data to compare the acoustic analysis results pre- and post-training.

The significance level was established at 0.05 (5%). The research conceptual framework is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Research Conceptual Framework

IV. FINDINGS

The results revealed that the Announcer Trainee pre- and post-training readings were correctly identified, on the average, in 80% of the announcer skill, showing that there are apparent differences when comparing the samples. The identification of the readings was done by means of perceptual analysis, which is a reliable and validated device for evaluating announcer skill. Even with the advance of analysis, perceptual evaluation has been traditionally used as an important clinical instrument. Two situations were considered for the analysis of the results listed in the reading identification, whether it was pre- or post-training, and the actual circumstance of the reading. The summarizes the results of the best Announcer' skill according to the identification and the actual circumstance of the reading. Results show that in 80% of the analysis, the samples identified as post training readings corresponded, in fact, to the recordings of the end of the course. Thus, it can be stated that a consumer rights

training for announcer of a radio announcing course is effective to develop certain communication skills, both for announcer who had a first contact with voice-over and for announcer who had some previous experience [9].

TABLE I
 THE ANNOUNCER TRAINEE PROGRAM ACCORDING TO THE IDENTIFICATION AND REAL SITUATION OF THE READING PRE- AND POST-TRAINING

Best Production			
IPosT-RPosT		IPosT-RPreT	
N	%	N	%
100	80	25	20

Abbreviations: IPosT, identified as posttraining; RPosT, real situation of posttraining; RPreT, real situation of pretraining.

Moreover, the announcer trainee program are developed, focusing on the following laws, consumer rights, Ethics respiratory-phonatory coordination, respiratory support and resistance, speech rate control, pitch, loudness, articulation, voice projection and resonance, speech rhythm variation, and punctuation. The vocal improvement approach includes exercises that promote adequate voice and speech adjustments for the radio setting, as well as the training of communication expressiveness resources.10 Such resources are related to melodic aspects of speech: intonation and emphasis of key words, pause, and modulation. To train the melodic aspects of speech, many texts —radio like or not— are used for loud reading with a focus also on communication creativity, spontaneity, and flexibility, which are some marked features of a voice-over professional.

TABLE II
 THE ANNOUNCER SKILL THAT CHARACTERIZED ACCORDING TO THE IDENTIFICATION AND REAL SITUATION OF THE READING PRE- AND POST-TRAINING

Parameters	Identification and Real Situation of the Reading					
	IPosT-RPosT		IPosT-RPreT		IPosT	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Use of emphasis	88	70.4	23	18.4	111	88.8
Type of voice	56	44.8	15	12.0	71	56.8
Pitch	51	40.8	7	5.6	58	46.4
Resonance	49	39.2	6	4.8	55	44.0
Speech rate	46	36.8	8	6.4	54	43.2
Articulation	45	36.0	14	11.2	59	47.2
Respiratory coordination	39	31.2	10	8.0	49	39.2
Loudness	34	27.2	7	5.6	41	32.8

Abbreviations: IPosT, identified as posttraining; RPosT, real situation of posttraining; RPreT, real situation of pretraining.

The announcer skill parameters that characterized readings are presented in Table II. To know the vocal perceptual parameters that changed with the training, judges were asked to point out which of the parameters determined by their rating. Emphasis (70.4%) and type of voice (44.8%) were the parameters that showed greater change with the voice and speech training. Other parameters, such as pitch (40.8%) and resonance (39.2%), also changed; however, this modification was not as obvious as the ones cited previously.

This fact demonstrates the importance of the knowledge utilization analysis for evaluating the laws, consumer rights, ethics and announcer skill selected parameters in this study;

and from the results obtained, it is possible to ponder about the role of speech and language pathology in the training of radio announcers and announcer of radio announcing, concerning both the content of the classes and the strategies and techniques adopted for certain learning situations.

This study confirms the announcer trainee program based on the development of specific vocal skills for radio announcers. Such premise may raise the thought that other professional voice users benefit from going through voice training and improvement programs. In this study, the use of emphasis was the vocal parameter that showed the most evident differences in the readings after the course; therefore,

melodic features may be developed and enhanced by the professional voice user. The NBTC of Thailand who creates strategies that involve these features can certainly perform a more efficient work with radio announcers [9].

V. CONCLUSION

The success of the announcer trainee program depends upon how well they communicate with others who must be skilled at laws, consumer rights, ethics and announcer skill include news analysts, reporters, and correspondents; interpreters and translators; salespersons and those in related occupations; and public relations specialists. Many announcers also must entertain their audience, so their work is similar to other entertainment-related occupations, such as actors, producers, and directors; and musicians, singers, and related workers. Some announcers write their own material, as do writers and editors [10]. Announcers perform a variety of duties, including some technical operations similar to those performed by broadcast and sound engineering technicians and radio operators. The NBTC of Thailand should decrease the competition for jobs as announcers will be keen because the broadcasting field attracts many more jobseekers than there are jobs. Furthermore, employment of announcers is projected to decline. In some cases, announcers leave the field because they cannot advance to better paying jobs. Changes in station ownership, format, and ratings frequently cause periods of unemployment for many announcers. Employment change. Employment of announcers is expected to decline moderately by 7 percent from 2006 to 2016. Increasing consolidation of radio and television stations, the advent of new technology, and growth of alternative media sources, such as satellite radio, will contribute to the expected decline. Consolidation among broadcasting companies may lead to an increased use of syndicated programming and programs originating outside a station's viewing or listening area [8].

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank Assoc. Prof. Dr. Luedech Girdwichai, The President of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand for financial support. Also, the author would like to thank to Asst. Prof. Dr. Prateep Wajeetongratana, the Dean of Faculty of Management Science for the full support in this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nogueira ALFR. Análise da constituição do estilo oral por radicalistic: um estudo fonético-acústico comparativo. In: Ferreira LP, ed. Dissertando sobre voz. Carapicuíba, Brazil: Pro'-Fono; 1998:63-98.
- [2] Medrado R, Ferreira LP, Behlau M. Voiceover: perceptual and acoustic analysis of vocal features. *J Voice*. 2005;19: 340-349.
- [3] Oliveira IB. Educação vocal na radiodifusão. In: Ferreira LP, ed. *Trabalhando a voz*. São Paulo, Brazil: Summus; 1988:28-39.
- [4] Farghaly SM. Deserto de um novo encontro: a estética vocal e a comunicação radiofônica. In: Ferreira LP, Silva- MAA, eds. *Saúde vocal: práticas fonoaudiológicas*. São Paulo, Brazil: Roca; 2002:169-173.

- [5] Timmermans B, De Bodt M, Wuyts FL, et al. Training outcome in future professional voice users after 18 months of voice training. *Folia Phoniatri Logop*. 2004;56:120-129.
- [6] Behlau M, Madazio G, Feijó D, et al. Avaliação de Voz. In: Behlau M, ed. *Voz: O livro do especialista*. Rio de Janeiro, Brazil: Revinter; 2001:85-245.
- [7] Kreiman J, Gerratt BR, Kempster GB, et al. Perceptual evaluation of voice quality: review, tutorial, and a framework for future research. *J Speech Hear Res*. 1993;36:21-40.
- [8] Behlau M, Feijó D, Madazio G, et al. Voz profissional: aspectos gerais e atuação fonoaudiológica. In: Behlau Med, *Voz: O livro do especialista*, Vol 2. São Paulo, Brazil: Revinter; 2005:287-408.
- [9] Sataloff RT. Introduction to treating voice abuse. In: Sataloff RT, ed. *Professional Voice: The Science and the Art of Clinical Care*. 2nd ed. San Diego, CA: Singular; 1997:691-693.
- [10] Borrego MCM. Expressividade no rádio. In: Kyrillos LR, ed. *Expressividade: da teoria à prática*. São Paulo, Brazil: Revinter; 2005:149-160.